

Key stakeholders mapping and functional requirements elicitation and analysis

D2.1

CiROCCO

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
D#	Deliverable #
DDS	Desert Dust Storm
EC	European Commission
EWS	Early Warning System
GA	Grant Agreement
PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almería
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
T#	Task #
WP	Work Package

H1 - Executive Summary

This Deliverable provides an overview of the activities carried out under T2.1 (*Stakeholder mapping and end-user needs analysis through processes of co-creation*), which primarily focuses on the identification of key stakeholders relevant to CiROCCO objectives and services and their enrolment in the Project's stakeholder community, as well as the elicitation and further analysis of CiROCCO system functional requirements, as perceived and expressed by the identified stakeholders, as a follow-up activity.

The structured approach was adopted to identify the relevant stakeholders, engage them in the CiROCCO Stakeholders' community and get valuable feedback from them to align, to the extent that this is possible, their needs and requirements with CiROCCO's expected outputs, which are described in detail in this Deliverable. Furthermore, targeted feedback from key stakeholders has been appropriately processed, and the identified end-user needs are also listed in this report.

The disclaimers included in this Deliverable, referring also to disclaimers included in Project questionnaires (in Annexes 2, 4, 6 and 8) have also been used in similar past projects, following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for CiROCCO (Grant Agreement number: 101086497).

H2 Goal / Objectives

The primary purpose of this Deliverable, as also indicated by its title, is the mapping of key stakeholders who are of direct relevance to CiROCCO activities and the elicitation and analysis of key stakeholders' needs and requirements that can be supported by the Project's activities and are at the same time of added value to CiROCCO. In more detail, the objectives of this Deliverable are to:

- Provide an overview of the approach adopted to establish a list of key stakeholders,
- Describe the procedure followed to get valuable feedback from stakeholders,
- Outline the primary outcomes from interaction with stakeholders and
- Present the critical end-user needs and requirements identified by stakeholders.

H3 Methodology

Identifying key stakeholders involved in CiROCCO was based on a structured approach, which involved considering the critical factors of a PESTLE analysis to determine domains to be represented inclusively. The active involvement of identified stakeholders from the beginning of the process had to be ensured so that the developed solutions would respond to end-user needs. The involvement, mobilisation and engagement of end-users were ensured through a participatory process, promoting technical capacity building. Targeted discussions and bilateral meetings, appropriate questionnaires and tailor-made stakeholders' workshops per pilot were the critical elements of this participatory process. A co-creation approach has been at the centre of the workshops to reach the objectives mentioned above and facilitate the extraction of end-user needs.

H4 Outcomes / Conclusions

The stakeholder mapping that was implemented in T2.1 and is described in D2.1 resulted in the establishment of a stakeholder canvas: a live document populated by Project partners with critical persons representing variable domains who have an interest in CiROCCO and can either affect or be affected by the Project or expertise in any component of the overall CiROCCO system. Upon identification of key stakeholders, a structured, participatory approach to retrieve feedback from them

was adopted, as presented above. A core element of this approach has been the organisation of targeted workshops tailored to the needs of each pilot. The outcomes of these workshops are also presented in this report.

Despite the variability of the needs and particularities of each pilot and, therefore, the variability in main topics raised during each workshop, it can be clearly stated that all workshop participants expressed a vivid interest in the CiROCCO system. Overall, stakeholders were actively involved during workshop implementation. They participated in fascinating and valuable discussions regarding the main challenges addressed by CiROCCO and the exploitation of CiROCCO outcomes not only during the lifetime of the Project but also during the post-project phase. Stakeholders also provided their feedback by responding to targeted questionnaires. The outcomes of the interaction with the stakeholders serve as a robust foundation for decision-making, ensuring the close alignment between CiROCCO Project outcomes and the expectations and needs of its diverse stakeholder base for all pilots, as will be examined later.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

The common needs among all four Pilots, as extracted from interaction with the stakeholders, include:

- Recording of meteo & air quality parameters with low-cost sensing nodes;
- Provision of robust external connectivity options for communication with a Cloud Server and other sensor networks;
- Offering a dedicated Dashboard for real-time monitoring, data analysis, and customisable alerts and
- Developing a high-quality system for enhanced accuracy in parameter recording.

The common requirements of all four Pilots, as extracted from interaction with the stakeholders, include:

- Enabling remote control and monitoring of nodes with automated and manual options;
- Low maintenance equipment with reliable and accurate measures and
- Facilitating maintenance and sensor replacement by personnel without specialised skills.

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Description

The work described in this Deliverable is part of the work carried out in *Work Package #2 (WP2) – Interactive Definition of User-oriented Requirements*. More specifically, this Deliverable summarises the main activities undertaken during the implementation of *Task 2.1: Stakeholder mapping and end-user needs analysis through the process of co-creation*, and the relevant outputs, including the stakeholder mapping and analysis and the methodological framework of the co-creation processes, providing assessment of end-user needs according to the results.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

The primary purpose of this Deliverable, as also indicated by its title, is the mapping of key stakeholders who are of direct relevance to CiROCCO activities and the elicitation and analysis of key stakeholders' needs and requirements that can supported by the Project's activities and are at the same time of added value to CiROCCO.

The structured approach adopted to identify the relevant stakeholders, engage them in the CiROCCO Stakeholders' community and get valuable feedback from them to align, to the extent that this is possible, their needs and requirements with the Project's expected outputs are described in detail in this Deliverable. Furthermore, targeted feedback already received from key stakeholders has been appropriately processed and the identified end-user needs, *i.e.* system features, are also listed in this report.

In more detail, the objectives of Deliverable 2.1 are to:

- Provide an overview of the approach adopted to establish a list of key stakeholders,
- Describe the procedure followed to get valuable feedback from stakeholders,
- Outline the primary outcomes from interaction with stakeholders,
- Present the critical end-user needs and requirements identified by stakeholders.

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.3. Intended Audience

This Deliverable is a public document available on the CiROCCO website after receiving approval from the European Commission (EC). The Project activities and the related outcomes discussed in this Deliverable are of direct interest to several target groups. The plan set out in this document is both shared knowledge among Project partners in terms of activities undertaken to get valuable feedback from stakeholders, outcomes from the analysis of this feedback, as well as a presentation towards wider audiences, offering the option for potential growth of the Project stakeholders' community, if needed. The intended audience is listed in the following:

1. All the members of the CiROCCO Consortium,
2. Pilot leaders,
3. Technical partners,
4. The EC, as the funding authority,

5. Stakeholders interested in the uptake of the CiROCCO system and
6. Other individuals or groups interested in obtaining further information about the Project.

Therefore, it is crucial that Project partners and a wider audience have access to and can consult it at all times.

1.4. Deliverable Structure and its Relation with Other Work Packages / Deliverables

This report is divided into seven Sections, followed by eight Annexes. A brief overview of the Deliverable structure is provided hereafter:

- **Section 1** is an introductory section of the document and provides a general overview of the Deliverable;
- **Section 2** presents how stakeholder mapping was structured and implemented in CiROCCO to establish the Stakeholder community;
- **Section 3** describes the participatory process and the co-creation approach adopted to retrieve valuable feedback from stakeholders;
- **Section 4** outlines the structure and primary outcomes of the workshops organised per pilot;
- **Section 5** summarises the primary stakeholders' needs, which are translated into system features and requirements identified from interactions with the stakeholders;
- **Section 6** summarises the conclusions of the Deliverable;
- **Section 7** includes the references of this Deliverable;
- **Annex 1** includes the results of the online survey from the first workshop (Pilot 2);
- **Annex 2** presents the questionnaire prepared for the first workshop (Pilot 2);
- **Annex 3** includes the results of the online survey from the second workshop (Pilot 3);
- **Annex 4** presents the questionnaire prepared for the second workshop (Pilot 3);
- **Annex 5** includes the results of the online survey from the third workshop (Pilot 1);
- **Annex 6** presents the questionnaire prepared for the third workshop (Pilot 1);
- **Annex 7** includes the results of the online survey from the fourth workshop (Pilot 4) and
- **Annex 8** presents the questionnaire prepared for the fourth workshop (Pilot 4)

The activities undertaken in T2.1 and described in this report, with a particular focus on the workshops organised under this Task, did not exclusively serve the needs of T2.1 (*Stakeholder mapping and end-user needs analysis through processes of co-creation*) but also the needs of T2.2 (*Pilot requirements and specifications for hard-to-reach under-sampled areas*), T3.1 (*Development of low-cost in-situ sensing nodes*), WP4 (*Pilots for improved geographical coverage and impact assessment*) in general and also T1.3 (*GDPR, gender balance, legal and ethical issues management*). Further to these, the purposes of T5.2 (*Capacity building, trainings and policy outreach on hard-to-reach areas*), T5.3 (*Coherent business model(s), exploitation activities and market-entry preparation plan*) and certainly T5.1 (*Dissemination, communication and liaison activities*) and T5.4 (*Collaboration with sister projects*) were also addressed by the activities undertaken in T2.1. Helpful feedback from the workshops has already been integrated into D5.3 and D5.5.

2. Stakeholder Mapping

Within CiROCCO, stakeholder mapping is foreseen to identify end-user needs and requirements related to CiROCCO further to or in support of those determined by pilot leaders. The involvement of stakeholders in the Project is critical and strongly encouraged, as key stakeholders are expected to bring additional experiences and perspectives to the decision-making processes. At the same time, such involvement enables stakeholder accountability in developing solutions to emerging issues they are called to address.

As discussed below, the task leader developed a structured approach for stakeholder mapping and communicated it to all partners, focusing on pilot leaders, who were asked to contribute to identifying key stakeholders. It has been essential to involve relevant stakeholders in CiROCCO since the early stages of the process. For this reason, the relevant activities were initiated from the very beginning of the Project.

A typical approach to identifying stakeholders includes the following steps:

- Identification of stakeholders,
- Analysis of their background, interests and expectations,
- Stakeholders' classification, usually based on their level of interest and influence,
- Stakeholders' prioritisation,
- Visual mapping,
- Identification and, when necessary, development of appropriate communication strategies that ensure their engagement and
- When relevant, establishment of regular contact to occasionally receive their feedback.

However, what is strongly needed in CiROCCO is the establishment of a long list of stakeholders with variable backgrounds that may typically participate in Project workshops and sometimes provide feedback on topics brought to discussion during the Project implementation. CiROCCO needs the identification of key stakeholders that are expected to be of added value to the Project, *i.e.*, stakeholders genuinely interested in the Project and its outputs, who will be invited and actively participate in local events and Project webinars and provide helpful feedback to Project partners.

Considering the above, stakeholder mapping in CiROCCO was performed following a slightly modified approach. Namely, the approach adopted included the following steps:

- Definition of "*CiROCCO external stakeholder*",
- Identification of different domains that need, or are of interest, to be represented,
- Identification of key stakeholders,
- Structured approach to reach out to stakeholders,
- Targeted approach, including the development of appropriate communication strategies to get valuable feedback and ensure their engagement and
- Establishment of regular contact to occasionally receive their feedback occasionally.

The different components of this procedure are analysed in more detail in the following Sections.

2.1. Definition of CiROCCO external stakeholders

The first step of the methodological procedure for stakeholder mapping that was followed in CiROCCO was the definition of the CiROCCO external stakeholders so that their role would become evident and distinct to both the partners who would approach them and, of course, to the stakeholders per se, when asked to join the CiROCCO stakeholder community. Because some Project partners are also local stakeholders (namely VSUME, MOL, DIMOS, CEDARE, and CSIC), it is clarified that the stakeholders discussed in this report refer exclusively to external stakeholders other than the Project partners.

CiROCCO stakeholder is a party interested in the CiROCCO Project and can either affect or be affected by the Project or **expertise** in any component of the overall CiROCCO system. This interest could be in datasets that will be collected during the Project implementation, processes and methodologies that will be developed and adopted, analyses that will be conducted and outputs and services that will be provided. The interest could be considered from a technical, academic, commercial and/or administrative perspective. Therefore, different domains to be represented by stakeholders were identified, as discussed in detail in Section 2.2.

2.2. Domains to be represented by stakeholders

Typical stakeholder groups that were considered to be examined as CiROCCO Stakeholders' pools include investors, customers, suppliers, communities, governments, and trade associations. For CiROCCO's specific objectives and outcomes, regional stakeholders, policy-makers, academics, technology experts, and innovative service providers are also potential stakeholders.

Considering the above and attempting to sufficiently identify the domains that needed to be represented by stakeholders within CiROCCO, a structured approach was followed. Potential stakeholders were initially sorted into two all-embracing categories: "*pilot-oriented stakeholders*" and "*horizontal stakeholders*". Pilot-oriented stakeholders include local and/or regional stakeholders who undertake relevant activity in any of the pilot areas and are interested or involved in relevant dataset analysis and monitoring of environmental conditions or are directly affected by CiROCCO outcomes. On the contrary to pilot-oriented stakeholders, horizontal stakeholders may represent the identified domains when considered from a more generic perspective, not necessarily focusing on one specific area or even relevant stakeholders representing areas other than the pilot areas.

Then, the critical factors considered in a PESTLE analysis [1] were examined, and a basic framework was used to identify domains to be represented within each one of the two initial stakeholder categories, complementary to those considered initially. These factors are namely the Political, the Economic, the Sociologic, the Technological, the Legal and the Environmental domains. Typically, these external (market) factors influence an organisation in terms of organ, performance and position in the marketplace and are mainly applied to identify opportunities and threats. Nevertheless, they can also be used in different contexts and in CiROCCO's case, they are used, as discussed above, to support stakeholder mapping.

Academics were also listed as pilot-oriented stakeholders, while academics, investors, and internal stakeholders were listed as horizontal stakeholders. Internal stakeholders are critical representatives from sister projects or other relevant ongoing or completed EU-funded projects and members of the Project Advisory Board. Specifically for the sister projects, since their objectives are aligned with the objectives of CiROCCO under a broader umbrella of goals set by EC, representatives from these

projects are also considered critical stakeholders welcomed to provide feedback and valuable insights to CiROCCO. As mentioned in Section 1.4, activities to engage stakeholder representatives from sister projects are aligned with clustering with sister projects undertaken under T5.4.

Figure 1 provides an overview of all critical domains identified to be represented by stakeholders in CiROCCO. Not all domains had to be necessarily defined within the CiROCCO stakeholder community; however, they served as a starting point for all partners to initiate identifying and reaching out to key stakeholders to bring them onboard to CiROCCO.

Pilot-oriented stakeholders	Horizontal stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political (Policy Makers) • Economic • Sociological • Technological (tech experts) • Legal • Environmental • Academics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political (Policy Makers, GEO thematic WGs) • Economic • Sociological • Technological (tech experts) • Legal • Environmental • Academics • Investors • Sister projects (internal stakeholders) • Advisory Board (internal stakeholders) • Other projects

Figure 1: Domains identified to be represented by CiROCCO stakeholders. The domains currently represented are marked with blue font.

2.3. Identification of key stakeholders

Upon identification of the domains to be represented by the stakeholders, an initial checklist was prepared and shared among all partners to be completed. Each partner was encouraged to suggest potential horizontal stakeholders (internal and external) to be approached, while pilot leaders, with the support of partners involved in each pilot, were encouraged to suggest potential pilot-oriented stakeholders. This checklist, the so-called CiROCCO Stakeholder canvas, is a live Excel document with different tabs for different stakeholder types shared in SharePoint, which includes, among other things, the organisation, expertise and country of stakeholders. The intention is to keep this list alive even after the completion of T2.1 and potentially include new additions, if relevant.

The purpose of having this list remains the same. The target is not to have an extended list of stakeholders but rather to have stakeholders who are expected to be of actual added value to CiROCCO, *i.e.*, stakeholders genuinely interested in the Project and its outputs, who will be invited and actively participate in local events and Project webinars and provide helpful feedback to Project partners.

2.4. Reaching out to stakeholders

A structured approach has been adopted to reach out to the stakeholders who have already been identified.

In many cases, ICCS proceeded to direct communication with the potential members of the stakeholder community, and apart from exchanging emails, most of the time, online meetings were

organised, aiming to familiarise them with the objectives and expected outcomes of CiROCCO and make an introduction to the expected contribution from them. In other cases, the partner who suggested a stakeholder initiated the communication with the potential member of the stakeholder community and further interactions (often physical meetings) followed. The ultimate purpose was to mobilise and engage them from the beginning of the process and ensure their active participation in the Project workshops. Minutes from the online meetings were kept, and the relevant project partners further discussed the critical topics raised internally.

A Layman's report was also prepared to facilitate reaching out to the correct audience. This Project brochure was circulated to the stakeholders and distributed during workshops and events. The CiROCCO brochure includes some basic information for the Project (aim, objectives, etc.), a high-level system architecture, the expected outputs (namely the CiROCCO services) and reference to the pilots (not focusing exclusively on them to avoid narrowing down the pool of stakeholders).

2.5. Retrieval of feedback from stakeholders

To ensure the engagement of stakeholders and retrieve valuable feedback from them, a targeted approach, including the development of tailored and contextualised engagement strategies and appropriate communication strategies, was adopted. More specifically, the following aspects were addressed:

- Fostering **discussions** about the local impacts, environmental, climate, business and social aspects,
- Preparation of **questionnaires for written feedback** customised to the needs and requirements of each pilot,
- Planning of **tailor-made workshops** (different approaches adopted for each pilot) to identify the actual needs of the end-users, challenges and requirements and any limitations they may experience to feed into technology and service design,
- Setting up online surveys for direct feedback during the workshops.

Overall, the participatory process and co-creation approach were endorsed, making the stakeholders part of the CiROCCO think tank. Further to ensuring stakeholders' engagement, the adopted approach enables awareness-raising and trust-building measures among stakeholders. The elements of this participatory process and co-creation approach are discussed in detail in Section 3.

2.6. Next steps in stakeholder mapping

Even though stakeholder mapping for T2.1 has been completed, relevant activities will be undertaken. In particular, regular contacts with the identified stakeholders will be established to receive their feedback occasionally. CiROCCO stakeholders will be asked to participate actively in upcoming workshops and webinars and will always be encouraged to give their input on issues of importance to the Project. In addition, as also discussed in Section 2.3, there is an intention to keep the stakeholder canvas alive even after the completion of T2.1 and potentially update the stakeholders' list, if relevant.

3. Participatory process and co-creation approach

The involvement, mobilisation and engagement of end-users were ensured through a participatory process, promoting technical capacity building. Targeted discussions and bilateral meetings, appropriate questionnaires and tailor-made stakeholders' workshops per pilot were the key elements of this participatory process. A co-creation approach has been at the centre of the workshops carried out to reach the objectives of T2.1 and facilitate the extraction of end-user needs. An overview of the different elements of the participatory process is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The key elements of the adopted participatory process.

3.1. Targeted discussions and bilateral meetings

Initial contacts with stakeholders were most often established through targeted discussions and bilateral meetings between ICCS and/or relevant Project partners and the stakeholders. Such discussions were either pilot-oriented when focused on a specific pilot and/or initiated by a pilot leader or horizontal when involving horizontal stakeholders, most typically stakeholders-partners from other projects and sister projects.

The topics around which the discussions were made, included local impacts, environmental, climate, business and social aspects of CiROCCO outcomes as T2.2 progressed with T2.1, initial outcomes from T2.2 (end-user needs and system features) also provided material for the targeted discussions with stakeholders.

Typically, such discussions and meetings precede a workshop. Nevertheless, when stakeholders' interest in CiROCCO was particularly strong, relevant meetings were repeated even after the workshop, and contacts were established on a regular basis.

3.2. Questionnaires

In an attempt to receive feedback from stakeholders more systematically, appropriate questionnaires were prepared. These questionnaires can be distinguished into two categories: questionnaires for written feedback and online surveys.

The **questionnaires for written feedback** were typically circulated to stakeholders before or during the workshop and asked to be filled out during (or shortly after) the workshop. In that way, the stakeholders were becoming familiar with the specific topics of the workshop beforehand. They had more time to elaborate on potential questions and suggestions during the workshop. Parallel to that, they were given sufficient time to elaborate on the questions and provide justified and solid replies. Nevertheless, the questionnaires are not necessarily linked to the workshops. In most pilots, they were filled out also by stakeholders who did not attend any workshop and only interacted directly with Project partners.

The questionnaires for all pilots were prepared following a generic structure, while for each pilot, the questions were adjusted correctly to fit its context and address its particular needs. The first part of the questionnaires included basic demographic features (age, gender, location, education level and occupation), followed by a limited number of open-ended questions on:

- the perception of the importance of the problem addressed by CiROCCO in a specific pilot,
- identification of other relevant stakeholders,
- identification of existing gaps in regulation,
- characterisation of the capacity of the stakeholders' organisation to tackle the problem addressed,
- indication of currently measured parameters in the stakeholder's area,
- other relevant measures/practices in place in the stakeholder's area,

Then, a couple of capacity development questions followed (for T5.2), referring to gaps in preparedness against the problem(s) discussed and current practice in central decision-making for the specific situation. Section 4 includes detailed information on the questionnaires per pilot.

Unlike the questionnaires, which are not necessarily linked with the workshops, **online surveys** are an inextricable part of the workshops as they were conducted during the workshop. Similar to the approach of the questionnaires for written feedback, the surveys for all pilots were prepared following a generic structure, which was then correctly adjusted to each pilot. The first part of the survey included basic demographic features (education level and organisation), followed by several questions (either open-ended or closed-ended) on:

- the perception of the importance of the problem addressed by CiROCCO in a specific pilot,
- the sufficiency of adopted measures and practices,
- identification of important parameters to be monitored,
- network coverage in the area of interest,
- desirable outputs from CiROCCO and
- potential CiROCCO outputs end-users.

A couple of capacity development questions followed (for T5.2), referring to preferable training activities and documentation to uptake solutions. Capacity Development Sections for the 1st and 2nd workshop are analysed in D5.3. Considering that some workshops were not implemented by the submission of D5.3, the analysis for the remaining workshops will be integrated into D5.4.

A dedicated exploitation Section was foreseen in the online surveys of the 2nd, 3rd and 4th workshops, as discussed in D5.5. Considering that some workshops were not implemented by the submission of D5.5, the analysis for the remaining workshops will be integrated into D5.6.

Section 4 includes detailed information on the online surveys per pilot.

3.3. Tailor-made Stakeholders' workshops per pilot

A co-creation approach has been adopted during the implementation of targeted workshops organised in the framework of Task 2.1. The overall structure of the workshops was originally planned before the first Stakeholder's workshop. It was tested during the first Workshop and kept being further improved and, where necessary, adjusted to the local context of pilots along with the progress of the Project.

3.3.1. Workshops' preparatory activities and structure

Before the workshop, several **preparatory bilateral meetings** were taking place between ICCS, the workshop organiser and T2.1 leader and the pilot leaders, to identify the main topics that should be discussed during each workshop, decide upon a list of key speakers that would present issues of interest and then set up the workshop agenda.

As mentioned in Section 1.4, these workshops did not exclusively serve the needs of T2.1. Still, also the needs of several other Tasks and the outcomes of the workshops could be directly exploited by most partners, namely ICCS (for T2.1, T4.6, T5.1 and T5.4), EBOS (for T2.2 and T3.1), NOA (for T5.2), INO (for T5.3), UCY (for T1.3) and Pilot leaders (for T4.2-T4.5). To this end, ICCS, as T2.1, T5.1 and T5.4 leaders, proceeded to **additional preparatory meetings** with EBOS, as T2.2 and T3.1 leader, NOA, as T5.2 leader and INO as T5.3 leader. The aim of these meetings was further elaboration on the topics to be discussed during the open-discussion sessions of the workshops and the identification of specific questions to be addressed to the workshop attendees, to get valuable feedback. Additional information on the **questionnaires** addressed to attendees, to be replied to either during or shortly after the workshops and the **online surveys**, to be replied to during the workshops, are presented in Section 3.2 above and Annexes 1-8.

A typical agenda included:

- Presentation of the main objectives, the expected results and the envisioned system of CiROCCO, focusing every time on the particularities of the pilot that hosted the workshop;
- presentations from key speakers highly relevant to each pilot;
- open discussions about the identified topics of interest;
- an online survey for direct feedback (in all cases the Mentimeter¹ interactive presentation software was selected as the appropriate tool to conduct the online survey);
- discussion on exploitation issues (a dedicated exploitation session was foreseen in the 2nd workshop and relevant questions were included in the online survey of the 3rd and the 4th Workshop).

In an attempt to encourage more active participation of stakeholders in the workshops, the language in which each workshop was conducted was properly selected. When stakeholders were fluent in English, all discussions were held in English, so that Project partners would easily follow and participate in the discussions; otherwise, the workshop was implemented in a mixture of English and local language, as discussed in more detail in Section 4.

Further to co-creation, social innovation aspects were addressed during the tailor-made workshops, because CiROCCO outputs and services, which were the main discussion topic during the workshops, have the ultimate purpose of improving the welfare and well-being of individuals and communities [2]. The Project's technological developments and the scientific research, both in the background (for

¹ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

these developments) and the foreground (after exploiting these developments), consider the effects and potential impacts on the environment and society, achieving thus Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) [3]. In addition, the workshops were set up considering also future oriented (foresight) methods, as the uptake of CiROCCO outcomes and services after the completion of the Project by potential end-users was strongly encouraged.

Figure 3 presents an overview of the structure of workshops, indicating how they address the key elements of the overall adopted participatory process presented in Figure 2.

Figure 3: An overview of the structure of workshops (in the centre), indicating (in blue font) how the workshops address the key elements of the CiROCCO participatory process.

3.3.2. Feedback analysis

The active involvement of pilot leaders in the analysis of feedback received from stakeholders has been essential for several reasons. First of all, there was a language barrier in some workshops, as during key speeches from stakeholders and open discussion slots the interaction was in local language for the reasons presented in Section 3.3.1. In addition, pilot leaders had further interactions with local stakeholders beyond their interaction during the workshop, *i.e.*, meetings before the workshops (for familiarizing with CiROCCO and establishing contacts) and after the workshops (for provision of clarifications, when needed, and collection of filled-in questionnaires). Therefore, the outputs of all interactions had to be considered to have an integrated feedback analysis.

The outcomes of the analysis of feedback retrieved from stakeholders are summarized in the following:

- Demographic statistics for the stakeholders who replied to questionnaires for written feedback,
- Graphs summarizing responses to the questionnaires for written feedback,
- A summary of key issues raised during the workshop and core workshop outputs and findings, mainly concerning stakeholders' needs translated into system features, and requirements,
- A graphical visualisation of the replies to the online survey (as directly provided by Mentimeter).

These outcomes were collected for all workshops and are discussed in more detail in Section 4 and Annexes 1, 3, 5 and 7.

4. Stakeholders' workshops: structure and main outcomes

4.1. 1st Stakeholders Workshop (Pilot 2)

4.1.1. General information for the workshop

In the Cypriot Pilot of the CiROCCO Project (Pilot 2), the identification and assessment of stakeholders' needs and requirements is essential. This crucial task unfolded during the 1st CiROCCO Stakeholders' workshop, the primary objectives of which were twofold. Firstly, to identify the differentiated needs and requirements of the diverse group of participants representing various regions and professional backgrounds. Secondly, to validate and reinforce these findings through a systematic questionnaire.

The workshop took place on **20.10.2023 (08:00 – 12:30 CET)**, in a **hybrid format** (both physical and online) and the event was hosted by our local partner UCY. The **venue** for those joining in person was the campus of the University of Cyprus in Nicosia, Cyprus, and the workshop was held in English language.

Workshop participants were characterized by demographic diversity, originating from various regions, including Cyprus, Greece, Serbia, and Lebanon. Additionally, they spanned a broad spectrum of educational backgrounds, ranging from students to PhD holders. The professional diversity was equally extensive, covering students, researchers, employed individuals, and those presently not engaged in work, thus providing a rich tapestry of data.

The following sections summarise the key findings of the 1st CiROCCO Stakeholders Workshop and insights derived from the questionnaire responses, shedding light on the multifaceted perspectives and requirements of the stakeholders involved.

4.1.2. Workshop structure

The workshop was organised into two Sessions, the *Local impact of DDS events* and the *CiROCCO Project and its contribution*. During the first Session, keynote speeches were foreseen aiming to set up the framework of the problem, focusing on local impacts and mainly the impact of DDS on human health, the environment and aviation. Open discussion on the topics addressed in the speeches followed the presentations.

During the second Session, an overview of CiROCCO and its expected contribution to Pilot 2 was presented by ICCS, while information about the National Action Plan for Dust was presented by UCY. Then a second round of open discussion was organised. The discussion was structured around specific topics and participants were asked to fill out the questionnaire in parallel. Then an online survey in Mentimeter was conducted, including questions tailored to the needs and the particularities of this pilot. The outputs of the online survey are presented in Annex 1.

The workshop agenda is presented below.

AGENDA

Time (EEST)	Description	Organisation	Presenter
09:00-09:30	Registration		
09:30-09:45	Welcome Greetings		
Local impacts of DDS events			
09:45-09:55	Sand storms, Dust storms and Aviation	EASA	Dr. Filippos Tymvios
09:55-10:05	Impacts of DDS events on the environment	UCY	Dr. Marina Neophytou
10:05-10:20	Impacts on DDS events on human health	UCY	Dr. Pinelopi Anagnostopoulou
10:20-10:35	Conclusions of the Life Medea project	UCY	Ms. Evi Kinni
10:35-11:00	Q/A and open discussion		All
11:00-11:30	Coffee break		
CiROCCO Project and its contribution			
11:30-11:45	CiROCCO Overview: Focusing on the Pilot of Cyprus	ICCS	Dr Chrysoula Papathanasiou
11:45-12:00	National Action Plan for Dust	UCY	Dr. Panayiotis Kouis
12:00-13:00	Open discussion		All
13:00-13:20	Online survey	ICCS	Kate Zouroufidou
13:20-13:30	Wrap-up and closing of the event	ICCS/UCY	Dr Chrysoula Papathanasiou

Figure 4: The agenda of the 1st CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop.

Photos captured during the workshop are presented below.

Figure 5: Photos from the 1st CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop.

4.1.3. Analysis of filled-in questionnaires for written feedback

Through active participation in the workshop, attendees provided valuable insights. Subsequently, these insights were reinforced through data gathered from structured questionnaires completed by a total of 21 individuals. These questionnaires were tailored to the needs of Pilot 2, addressing the particularities of the pilot area and the expected needs and requirements of stakeholders. They were either circulated and filled in during the workshops by the workshop attendees or sent at a later stage via email to additional stakeholders (who could not join the workshop).

The questionnaire for written feedback is included in Annex 2. The analysis of the feedback started upon gathering all filled-in questionnaires, the responses received were summarized and are visualized in the following figures.

Figure 6a-e: Demographic features of the respondents to the questionnaire for written feedback for the Cypriot pilot.

Figure 7a-j: Replies to the questions Q1 (Figure 7a) - Q8 (Figure 7j) of the questionnaire for written feedback for the Cypriot pilot.

4.1.4. Main outcomes

The CiROCCO sensing node system for Pilot 2 outlines specific requirements that need to be met before it can be adopted by national authorities. These requirements come from the discussions at the stakeholders' workshop, the responses to the questionnaires, and the pilot's research and operational needs. Aligned with these objectives, the design of the sensing nodes incorporates tailored features, addressing distinct needs and requirements to guarantee optimal functionality and scalability within Mediterranean regions affected by DDS. The main outcomes from the interaction with stakeholders for Pilot 2 are summarized in the following.

- **76%** of participants consider **DDS** to be an **extremely important or important problem** in their area,
- In addressing the issue of DDS events, **45%** of respondents see **Governmental Bodies** as primarily responsible, followed by **18%** who believe **scientific and research institutions** should take the lead. This question allowed for multiple responses.
- **39%** of respondents identified a **lack of legislative framework** in the current regulation of DDS.
- The **health sector** is perceived as the **most affected by DDS**, with **75%** of responses indicating this.

- For better preparation against upcoming DDS events, **29%** of respondents highlighted **situational awareness** as key, while **21%** emphasized the importance of **education and training**.
- Approx. **53%** of participants believe that **more in-situ data** would help address the DDS issue in their area. Notably, approx. **48%** of interviewees **did not respond to this question, possibly due to limited knowledge of the topic**.
- Given the limited information available, participants recommended more **targeted information campaigns and training for the general population** on adapting to DDS-related problems.

4.2. 2nd Stakeholders Workshop (Pilot 3)

4.2.1. General information for the workshop

In the Serbian Pilot of the CiROCCO Project (Pilot 3), the gathering of valuable feedback from local, regional and national stakeholders has also been an issue of priority. To this end, the 2nd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop was organized and properly structured to efficiently get this feedback in the end.

The workshop took place on **05.12.2023 (09:30 – 14:30 CET)**, in a **hybrid format** and the event was hosted by our local partner VSUME. The **venue** for those joining in person was the campus of the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Natural Sciences, in Novi Sad, Serbia. The 2nd Workshop was held both in English and Serbian language to facilitate the attendees. More specifically, all open discussions were made in Serbian so that local stakeholders would be encouraged to provide valuable feedback without being obstructed by the language barrier. At the same time, all presentations (coming from either Project partners or stakeholders) were made in English, so that non-Serbian attendees would be able to keep track of the discussions made during the workshop and when needed interact with local stakeholders.

Workshop attendees represented a broad spectrum of educational backgrounds, ranging from engineers to PhD holders. Participants were coming from the governmental sector, as well as from private and scientific-research one.

The following sections summarise the key findings of the 2nd CiROCCO Stakeholders Workshop and insights derived from the questionnaire responses, as well as the outcomes of preparatory bilateral meetings between Project partners and key stakeholders, shedding light on the multifaceted perspectives and requirements of the stakeholders involved.

4.2.2. Workshop structure

The workshop was organised into three Sessions, *Sustainable environmental restoration support, CiROCCO Project and its contribution* and *Exploitation workshop and online survey*. During the first Session and after the presentation of an introductory overview of the CiROCCO Project by ICCS, keynote speeches, some of them from VSUME, were foreseen aiming to set up the framework of the problem. These speeches focused on local impacts and mainly forest management and fire protection in the vulnerable pilot site, which is a protected area and air quality monitoring in the greater area.

During the second session, more details about the Serbian pilot and the CiROCCO low-cost system were presented by EBOS. A plenary discussion, during which the questionnaires for written feedback

were circulated to the attendees, followed these presentations. The discussion was structured around pilot-oriented topics and participants were asked to fill out the questionnaire in parallel.

The open discussion was succeeded by a joint exploitation workshop and an online survey using Mentimeter, including questions tailored to the needs and the particularities of the Serbian pilot, led by INO. The outputs of the exploitation workshop and the online survey are presented in Annex 3.

The workshop agenda is presented below.

AGENDA

Date & Place: 5th of December 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia
Hybrid event – please register by following the link at the end of document.

Time (CET)	Description	Organisation	Presenter
09:30-10:00	Registration		
10:00-10:15	Welcome Greetings		
Sustainable Environmental Restoration Support			
10:15-10:30	Horizon CiROCCO Project Overview	ICCS	Dr Chrysoula Papathanasiou
10:30-10:45	Sustainable management of Deliblato Sands protected area	PE Vojvodinašume	Ivana Vasić
10:45-11:00	Forest management and fire protection in Deliblato Sands protected area	PE Vojvodinašume	Sladana Dabić
11:00-11:15	Advanced monitoring of ambient air quality in the automated monitoring network of AP Vojvodina	APV	mr Hristina Radovanović-Jovin
Coffee break 15 min			
11:30-11:45	CiROCCO Pilot in Serbia: Requirements for sensors, ecological modelling, risk management and mitigation planning	INO	Dr Minučer Mesaroš
11:45-12:00	Enabling in-situ, environmental monitoring using low-cost, sensing nodes for hard-to-reach areas	eBOS	Dr Marios Sophocleous
12:00-12:30	Plenary discussion		
12:30-13:00	Exploitation workshop & online survey	INO	Jelena Đokić
13:00-13:10	Wrap-up and closing of the event	ICCS/VSUME	Ivana Vasić
13:15-14:30	Lunch		

Figure 8: The agenda of the 2nd CiROCCO Stakeholders’ Workshop.

Photos captured during the workshop are presented below.

Figure 9: Photos from the 2nd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop.

4.2.3. Analysis of filled-in questionnaires for written feedback

Workshop attendees actively participated in the open discussions and filled out questionnaires tailored to the needs of Pilot 3, addressing the particularities of the pilot area and expected needs and requirements from stakeholders. The questionnaires for written feedback were filled out during and after the workshop and were eventually completed by a total of 20 individuals. This questionnaire is included in Annex 4 and the following figures summarise an analysis of the responses received.

Figure 10: Demographic features of the respondents to the questionnaire for written feedback for the Serbian pilot.

Figure 11a-j: Replies to the questions Q1 (Figure 11a) - Q8 (Figure 11j) of the questionnaire for written feedback for the Serbian pilot.

4.2.4. Main outcomes

For the uptake of CiROCCO system for Pilot 3 from local/regional/national authorities, end-user needs and specific requirements were examined. An integrated analysis of responses to questionnaires for written feedback, replies to the online survey and topics raised and discussed during the workshop, as well as during pre- and post-workshop meetings with local stakeholders results in the following summary of outcomes from interaction with stakeholders for pilot 3.

- **34%** of participants consider **air quality** as a problem with **moderate** frequency,
- **89%** of participants consider **fire risks to be a very important or important problem** in their area and have a **high impact with low frequency**,
- **54%** of the participants think that **current measures and practices are inadequate or ineffective** to decrease air pollution,
- Most **important parameters** to be monitored are **PM₁₀, PM_{2,5}, Ozone, NO₂, wind direction, and air temperature**,
- **All** participants consider CO₂ emission as the **main indicator** for assessing the **impacts of fires** and the creation of relevant measures,
- **45%** of the participants consider **CiROCCO system relevant for other sectors** (agriculture, industry, etc.),
- **75%** think that **prediction models** would be most important,
- **88%** would like to have **3-day predictions in advance**,
- **66%** of the participants think that the **Agency for Environmental Protection and National Hydro-meteorological Institute would have benefited from CiROCCO system**,
- **55%** of the participants would like to have **on-work trainings and workshops** for applying CiROCCO solutions.

4.3. 3rd Stakeholders Workshop (Pilot 1)

4.3.1. General information for the workshop

Similar to the other workshops, the 3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop was organized for the Egyptian Pilot of CiROCCO Project (Pilot 1) to gather useful feedback from local and national stakeholders on CiROCCO system. Hence, the workshop was properly structured to efficiently get this valuable feedback.

The workshop took place on **22.01.2024 (09:30 – 14:30 CET)**, in a **hybrid format** and the event was hosted by our local partner CEDARE. The **venue** for those joining in person was the Inter-Continental

Cairo Semiramis Hotel, in Cairo, Egypt, and the workshop was held exclusively in English (both presentations and discussions). On 24.01.2024 a **field trip to the pilot site**, the Benban solar farm, as well as to the greater area of Aswan was organized by CEDARE, aiming to familiarize all stakeholders with the particularities of these sites and foster further targeted interactions with stakeholders.

Participants represented a diverse demographic, originating from various regions, including Egypt, Cyprus, Greece, and Serbia. They also spanned a broad spectrum of educational backgrounds, ranging from students to PhD holders. As for the professional diversity, it was equally extensive, covering representatives from the local society, students, researchers, employed individuals, and those presently not engaged in work.

The following sections summarise the key findings of the 3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders Workshop and insights derived from the questionnaire responses, shedding light on the multifaceted perspectives and requirements of the stakeholders involved.

4.3.2. Workshop structure

As was the case with the previous workshops, this workshop was organised into three Sessions, *Renewable energy systems planning*, *CiROCCO Project and its contribution* and *Exploitation workshop and online survey*. During the first Session and after the presentation of an introductory overview of the CiROCCO Project by ICCS, keynote speeches were foreseen aiming to set up the framework of the problem and provide an overview of recent updates in the field. These updates referred to the solar atlas and a follow-up on the local pilot, as presented by CEDARE, as well as government views on the issue overall. Open discussion on the topics addressed in the speeches followed the presentations.

During the second Session additional information on the CiROCCO system, focusing on the in-situ low-cost sensing nodes, was presented by EBOS, while an overview of CiROCCO and its expected contribution to Pilot 1 was presented by NOA. Then a second round of plenary discussion was organised. The discussion was structured around specific, pilot-oriented topics and participants were asked to fill out the questionnaire in parallel.

A joint online survey, including exploitation questions as well as other questions of direct interest to CiROCCO tailored to the needs and the particularities of Pilot 1, was conducted during the third Session. The joint online survey was implemented using Mentimeter. The outputs of the online survey are presented in Annex 5.

The workshop agenda is presented below.

AGENDA

Date & Place: 22nd of January 2024, Cairo, Egypt

Time (CET)	Description	Organization	Presenter
09:30-10:00	Registration		
10:00-10:15	Welcome Greetings		
Renewable Energy Systems Planning			
10:15-10:30	Horizon CiROCCO Project Overview	ICCS	Dr. Chrysoula Papathanasiou
10:30-10:45	Solar Atlas and follow up on local case study for CiROCCO	CEDARE	Dr. Hesham El-Askary
10:45-11:00	Government views	NREA	Dr. Mohamed El-Khayat
11:00-11:15	Q&A	All	Eng. Salma Mohamed
Coffee Break (15 mins)			
11:30-11:45	CiROCCO Pilot in Egypt: Requirements for sensors, ecological modelling, risk management and mitigation planning	eBOS	Dr. Marios Sophocleous
11:45-12:00	Enabling in-situ, environmental monitoring using low-cost, sensing nodes for hard-to-reach areas: Usefulness for renewable energy applications	NOA	Dr. Panagiotis Kosmopoulos
12:00-12:30	Plenary Discussion		
12:30-13:00	Exploitation workshop & online survey	CEDARE	Dr. Hesham / Dr. Omar
13:00-13:10	Wrap-up and closing of the event	CEDARE	Dr. Omar Elbadawy
13:15-14:30	Lunch		

Figure 12: The agenda of the 3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders’ Workshop.

Photos captured during the workshop are presented below.

Figure 13: Photos from the 3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders’ Workshop.

4.3.3. Analysis of filled-in questionnaires for written feedback

Workshop attendees participated actively in the workshop and provided valuable feedback. The 3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop provided the primary source of information, with participants

actively contributing their viewpoints. To guarantee an effective validation procedure, questionnaires for written feedback were circulated to 28 individuals. The people who took part offered a rich tapestry of data, varying in professional background and place of origin. This methodological fusion attempted to extract a comprehensive understanding of the requirements and needs of stakeholders, serving as the foundation for decisions made later in the project.

The questionnaires could optionally be returned to local partners (CEDARE) within a week, in case the participants needed more time to fill them in. Stakeholders who did not manage to join the workshop were also asked to fill in these questionnaires and send them back to CEDARE within a week. The questionnaire for written feedback that was distributed during the 3rd workshop is included in Annex 6 and the following figures summarise an analysis of the responses received.

Figure 14a-e: Demographic features of the respondents to the questionnaire for written feedback for the Egyptian pilot.

Figure 15a-l: Replies to the questions Q1 (Figure 15a) – Q10 (Figure 15l) of the questionnaire for written feedback for the Egyptian pilot.

4.3.4. Main outcomes

For the uptake of CiROCCO system for Pilot 1 from regional and national authorities, end-user needs and specific requirements were examined. The responses to questionnaires for written feedback, the replies to the online survey and the topics raised and discussed with local stakeholders before, during and after the workshop were analysed and the main outcomes from these interactions with stakeholders are summarized in the following.

- More than **35%** of participants consider **DDS** to be an **extremely important or important problem** in their area that affects the air quality and energy production,
- Approx. **25%** of the participants agreed that **dust deposition** is one of the **most important parameters** that will be useful in monitoring dust, solar energy potential and air quality,
- The **Electricity and Renewable Energy sector** is perceived as the **most affected by DDS**, with **80%** of responses indicating this,
- For better preparation against upcoming DDS events, **30%** of respondents highlighted **situational awareness** as key, with approx. **20%** of the respondents emphasised the importance of **education and training**,
- **45%** of the participants consider the **workshops** as an efficient training way to come up with solutions for CiROCCO, while **39%** think that **on-the-job trainings with long-term support** are more efficient way,
- Participants recommended more **targeted information campaigns and training for the general population** on adapting to DDS-related problems.

4.4. 4th Stakeholders Workshop (Pilot 4)

4.4.1. General information for the workshop

The 4th CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop was organized for the Spanish Pilot of CiROCCO Project (Pilot 4) to enable interaction with local stakeholders, familiarise them with the Project objectives and outcomes and eventually retrieve useful feedback from them on CiROCCO system. The workshop was properly structured to efficiently achieve its purpose.

The workshop took place on **08.03.2024 (09:30 – 13:10 CET)**, in **virtual format** and the event was hosted by our local partner in Almeria, Spain, CSIC. The 4th Workshop was held both in English and Spanish language to facilitate the attendees. In particular, all open discussions were made in Spanish so that local stakeholders would be encouraged to provide valuable feedback without being obstructed by the language barrier. At the same time, all presentations (coming from either Project

partners or stakeholders) were made in English, so that non-Spanish attendees would be able to keep track of the discussions made during the workshop and when needed interact with local stakeholders.

Workshop participants represented mainly southern Spain, a range of ages between 30 and 65 years. Their educational background ranged from Bachelor's degrees to PhD holders. Most of the attendees were researchers, followed by public agency representatives.

The following sections summarise the key findings of the 4th CiROCCO Stakeholders Workshop and insights derived from the questionnaire responses, as well as the outcomes of preparatory bilateral meetings between Project partners and key stakeholders, shedding light on the multifaceted perspectives and requirements of the stakeholders involved.

4.4.2. Workshop structure

The structure of the workshop was similar to the one followed in other Workshops. More specifically, the workshop was organized into three Sessions, *Local impacts of DDS events*, the *CiROCCO Project and its contribution* and *Exploitation workshop* and an integrated *online survey*. During the first Session, an introductory overview of the CiROCCO Project was presented by ICCS, while keynote speeches were foreseen aiming to set up the framework of the problem and provide an overview of the current status. A slot for open discussion on the topics addressed in the speeches followed the presentations.

During the second Session additional information on the CiROCCO system, focusing on the in-situ low-cost sensing nodes, was presented by EBOS, the foreseen assimilation of satellite data and validation with in-situ measurements was presented by NOA and some details on the Spanish pilot, focusing on the impact of DDS events on water quality was presented by CSIC. Then a second round of plenary discussion was organized, structured around specific, pilot-oriented topics.

The third Session included an integrated online survey, which included exploitation questions as well as other questions of direct interest to CiROCCO tailored to the needs and the particularities of Pilot 4. The joint online survey was implemented using Mentimeter and its outputs are presented in Annex 7.

The workshop agenda is presented below.

AGENDA

Time (CET)	Description	Organisation	Presenter
09:30-09:40	Opening / Registration		
09:40-09:50	Welcome Greetings		
Local impacts of DDS events			
09:50-10:00	Horizon CiROCCO Project Overview	ICCS	Dr Chrysoula Papathanasiou
10:00-10:10	Monitoring atmospheric aerosols: from a local to international perspective	UGR	Dr Juan Luis Guerrero Rascado
10:10-10:20	Biocrust control in soil erosion and global dust emissions	UAL	Dr Emilio Rodríguez Caballero
10:20-10:30	Impact of Aerosols on Concentrating Solar Technology. The Experience of the "Plataforma Solar de Almería"	CIEMAT	Dr Jesús Ballestrín
10:30-11:00	Q/A and open discussion		All
11:00-11:15	Break		
CiROCCO Project and its contribution			
11:15-11:30	Enabling in-situ, environmental monitoring using low-cost, sensing nodes for hard-to reach areas. Requirements, usefulness, risks	EBOS	Dr Marios Sophocleus
11:30-11:45	Assimilation of satellite data and its validation through in situ measurements	NOA	Dr Eleni Drakaki
11:45-12:00	CiROCCO Overview: Focusing on the Spanish Pilot: DSS impact on water quality	CSIC	Dr Francisco Alcalá
12:00-12:30	Plenary discussion		All
12:30-12:50	Online survey	CSIC	Eng. Raúl Segura
12:50-13:10	Wrap-up and closing of the event	CSIC	Dr Francisco Alcalá

Figure 16: The agenda of the 4th CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop.

Photos captured during the online workshop are presented below.

Figure 17: Photos from the 4th CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop.

4.4.3. Analysis of filled-in questionnaires for written feedback

As the workshop was fully virtual, questionnaires for written feedback were provided to stakeholders both before and after the workshop and they were asked to provide their feedback to local partners (CSIC). Apart from workshop attendees, the questionnaire was also circulated to stakeholders who did not manage to join the workshop. The circulated questionnaire for written feedback is included in Annex 8. As the workshop was implemented very close to the submission deadline of this report and some filled-in questionnaires are still pending to be received from stakeholders, their analysis is omitted from D2.1. However, this analysis will be completed in the upcoming period and its outcomes will certainly be weighed in the design of the final functional requirements of the CiROCCO system.

4.4.4. Main outcomes

Workshop attendees participated actively in the workshop and the 4th CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop provided the primary source of feedback from stakeholders. To guarantee an effective validation procedure, questionnaires for written feedback were circulated to be filled out by individuals. As not all filled-out questionnaires were available before the completion of this report, oral feedback from discussions during the workshop was co-evaluated with feedback retrieved from unofficial internal interactions between Project partners and stakeholders for the Spanish pilot.

The main outcomes from these interactions with stakeholders are summarized in the following. It is mentioned here that in the absence of written feedback, relevant statistics (referring for example to the percentage of respondents who supported a statement) could not be easily extracted for Pilot 4. Nevertheless, a qualitative analysis of the main outcomes is presented below:

- Participants consider **air pollution** a **moderate problem**, in terms of impact and frequency in their area,
- For **groundwater quality degradation**, their characterization would go span from “**high impact and low frequency**” to “**high impact and high frequency**”,

- For both air pollution and groundwater quality degradation, they think the **mitigation measures are completely insufficient**,
- Stakeholders representing natural areas (including natural protected areas and relevant administrations), were mostly interested in how the **DDS events**, and the solutions proposed by the Project, **impact the management of their corresponding areas** (spatial planning and land use, natural resources management, sectoral economic activities and preservation/management of natural areas),
- The performance of the **AOD parameter under unsteady non-stationary atmospheric conditions over time** was further discussed between a representative of the Almeria Solar Platform (Plataforma Solar de Almería – PSA) and NOA and is a factor to be considered in data assimilation,
- CiROCCO would be characterized as a **moderate replicability** Project by Spanish stakeholders,
- Participants recommended targeted information campaigns and training for the general population on adapting to DDS-related problems.

5. System features and requirements as retrieved from stakeholders

The functional requirements of the CiROCCO system were outlined at a high level in the Grant Agreement (GA) and they are further elaborated and refined as the Project progresses. Focusing on functional requirements for the pilots, they are analysed in depth by pilot leaders in the framework of T2.2, but they are also shaped to a significant extent by (local) stakeholders. This latter is taking place in the framework of T2.1 through the participatory processes that are taking place, as presented above. Hence, T2.1 and T2.2 run in parallel and the outcomes of one Task were used as useful input to the other Task and vice versa. Especially for T2.1, feedback received from pilot leaders in T2.2 as needs, challenges and/or requirements in a Pilot was further elaborated and often verified by local stakeholders during the workshops of T2.1.

It should be noted that no significant deviations from the original system design are expected due to this co-design and co-definition of pilot needs and requirements (as they are identified by both pilot leaders and key pilot-oriented and horizontal stakeholders).

A summary of the system features and requirements that were retrieved from all types of interactions with CiROCCO stakeholders for the different pilots is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The key system features and requirements retrieved from interactions with stakeholders.

No.	Needs	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4
01	Recording of meteo & air quality parameters with low-cost sensing nodes	x	x	x	x
02	Recording of parameters to monitor land degradation and fire risk			x	
03	Environmental risk assessment (droughts, fires, land degradation, air pollution etc.)			x	
04	Provision of robust external connectivity options for communication with a Cloud Server and other sensor networks	x	x	x	x
05	Offering a dedicated Dashboard for real-time monitoring, data analysis, and customizable alerts	x	x	x	x
06	Accessing the information via maps				x
07	Ensuring secure and tiered access to sensor data for registered users	x	x	x	
08	Developing a high-quality system for enhanced accuracy in parameter recording	x	x	x	x

09	Enabling remote control and monitoring of nodes, with automated and manual options	x	x	x	x
10	Allowing for rapid and straightforward relocation of sensing nodes to adapt to monitoring demands	x	x	x	
11	Maintaining system compatibility and integration with an (Android-based and/or IOS-based) Early Warning System (EWS)	x	x		x
12	Providing the capability to expand the system with additional sensors in the future	x	x	x	
13	Low-maintenance equipment with reliable and accurate measures	x	x	x	x
14	Facilitating maintenance and sensor replacement by personnel without specialized skills	x	x	x	x
15	Provide suggestions on data usage from this sensor				x
16	Provide Project sustainability by transferring the sensor system to some competent national institutions (protected land manager, public bodies, Provincial institute for nature conservation, etc.) or having several institutions jointly manage it.			x	
17	Having a forecasting lead time of 3 days, and a spatial resolution from regional to Mediterranean				x

6. Conclusions

An overview of the activities carried out under T2.1 is presented in this Deliverable. The outcomes of these activities are summarized into:

- The establishment of the CiROCCO stakeholder community,
- The retrieval of valuable feedback from stakeholders on the main challenges posed by the different pilot areas and addressed in CiROCCO and
- The identification of crucial end-user needs and requirements identified by stakeholders.

The structured stakeholder mapping discussed in Section 2 resulted in the establishment of a stakeholder canvas: a live document populated by Project partners with critical persons representing variable domains, who have an interest in CiROCCO and can either affect or be affected by the Project or expertise in any component of the overall CiROCCO system. It is also mentioned here that there is an intention to keep this stakeholder canvas alive even after the completion of T2.1 and potentially update the stakeholders' list, if relevant.

Upon identifying key stakeholders, a structured, participatory approach to obtaining feedback from them was adopted, as presented in Sections 3 and 4. A core element of this participatory approach has been the organisation of targeted workshops tailored to the needs of each pilot. The outcomes of these workshops are also presented in Section 4.

Despite the variability of the needs and particularities of each pilot and, therefore, the variability in main topics raised during each workshop, it can be clearly stated that in all workshop participants expressed a vivid interest in the CiROCCO system. In general, stakeholders were actively involved during workshop implementation; they participated in fascinating and valuable discussions regarding the main challenges addressed by CiROCCO and the exploitation of CiROCCO outcomes not only during the lifetime of the Project but also during a post-project phase. Stakeholders also provided their feedback by responding to targeted questionnaires.

The standard system features and requirements among all four Pilots, as extracted from interaction with stakeholders, are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: The common system features and requirements among all four Pilots, as retrieved from interactions with stakeholders.

Common system features and requirements
Recording of meteo & air quality parameters with low-cost sensing nodes
Provision of robust external connectivity options for communication with a Cloud Server and other sensor networks
Offering a dedicated Dashboard for real-time monitoring, data analysis, and customizable alerts
Developing a high-quality system for enhanced accuracy in parameter recording
Enabling remote control and monitoring of nodes, with automated and manual options
Low-maintenance equipment with reliable and accurate measures

Facilitating maintenance and sensor replacement by personnel without specialized skills

Overall, the interaction outcomes with the stakeholders serve as a robust foundation for decision-making, ensuring that the CiROCCO Project aligns closely with the expectations and needs of its diverse stakeholder base for all pilots, as they will be examined later. The iterative and inclusive approach to gathering insights has laid the groundwork for a more responsive and adaptive project framework.

7. References

- [1] Jeffs, C. (2008), *Strategic planning and control in organisations*, Strategic Management, pp. 20-26, SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446216446>.
- [2] do Adro, F., Fernandes, C.I., *Social innovation: a systematic literature review and future agenda research*, Int Rev Public Nonprofit Mark 17, 23–40 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12208-019-00241-3>.
- [3] European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Options for strengthening responsible research and innovation – Report of the Expert Group on the State of Art in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation*, Publications Office, 2013, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/46253>.

Annexes

Annex 1: Online survey results from the 1st Stakeholders' Workshop

The graphical visualisation of the replies to the online survey is presented in this Annex.

Education Level
14 responses

Organisation
12 responses

How would you characterize the problem of DDS in your area?
6 responses

Characterization	Count
High impact - Low frequency	2
Low impact - High frequency	0
Moderate impact - Moderate frequency	4
Other Combination (specify in next slide)	5

How sufficient do you consider the measures and practices adopted to minimize the impact of DDS events in your area?

Rating (1-5)	Count
1 (Strongly disagree)	0
2	0
3	17
4	16
5 (Strongly agree)	13

Please rate the following parameters in terms of importance starting from the most important

Rank	Parameter
1st	Air temperature
2nd	PM-10
3rd	PM-2.5
4th	Wind speed
5th	Wind direction
6th	Ozone+NO2
7th	Humidity
8th	Atmospheric pressure
9th	Solar radiation
10th	Soil Moisture
11th	Soil Temperature

Which of these parameters seem attractive to monitor?

Parameter	Count
CO2	3
Dust emission flux	3
Air Quality Index	8
Dust deposition	6
Transport Pathways	2
Other (specify in next slide)	0

On average, how far are the desert sides from any type of network coverage?

Distance	Count
10km	2
20km	0
30km	0
50km	0
100km	0
200km	0
Other (specify in next slide)	1

What kind of forecasts (in terms of spatial resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

What kind of predictions would you like to see that would be helpful?

4 responses

- 1 km
- daily
- More spatial coverage
- 3 day forecast

What kind of forecasts (in terms of temporal resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

What kind of forecasts (in terms of temporal resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

1 response

- Daily!

Who do you think would need this system?

Who do you think would need this system?

4 responses

- Local authorities
- Universities
- Citizens
- Academic organizations

Compared to existing weather stations, which features of CiROCCO seem unique and attractive to you?

Compared to existing weather stations, which features seem unique and attractive to you?

1 response

- Operating in harsh environments

Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/ see fit, so that you ultimately efficiently uptake the solutions proposed? (not all)

Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/ see fit, so that you ultimately efficiently uptake the solutions proposed?

1 response

- Mobile app

Which modalities of tool documentation you find preferable, so as to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CIROCCO solutions (not all)

Which modalities of tool documentation you find preferable, so as to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CIROCCO solutions
1 response

Tech support

What information would you like to see on the CIROCCO platform that would be useful for your case?
6 responses

- Progress report, timeline
- Dashboard data
- Updates on the monitoring and network connectivity. Shareable data
- Dust dense mapping with accurate/verified measurements
- Interactive map
- Sensitivity maps

Annex 2: 1st Stakeholders' Workshop – Questionnaire for written feedback

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts – CiROCCO

1st CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop
20th of October 2023

Grant Agreement Number: 101086497

Name²:

Organisation*:

Email*:

Age*: <20 / 21-30 / 31-40 / 41-50 / 51-60 / 61-70 / 71-80

Gender*: male / female / other

Location* (Country/City):

Education Level*: School / Bachelor / Masters / PhD / Other (please specify)

Occupation*: Student (e.g. High-School or University) / Researcher / Employee / Not working (e.g. retired or unemployed)

² I consent to my contact details (First and Last Name, Organisation, etc.) being included in the list of participants.

- I understand that any personal data collected by CiROCCO will be kept strictly confidential, to the minimum necessary for the purpose.
- I understand my data subjects rights*
- I understand that my participation raises some small risks** in terms of entrusting my data to the research team.
- I consent to being filmed, audio recorded, and having notes taken of my activities and experiences during the workshop/webinar and consent to CiROCCO using this for its promotion.
- I understand that if I have any questions seeking further clarification or assurances about the ethical issues relating to the project, I am free to contact the Project Coordinator, Dr. Angelos Amditis.

*"You have the right to information regarding what is collected and processed, to access to your data being processed, to delete or make any changes to this information, and to restrict processing. You have the right to receive requested information in a time-limited fashion. If you are concerned or have questions about how your personal data is being processed, you have the right to contact both the Project Coordinator, Dr Angelos Amditis, and the communication Project manager, Ms. Kate Zouroufidou."

**"There is a small risk that you may share some confidential information by chance or that you may feel uncomfortable talking about some issues. You can inform us at any time, if you decide you do not want to have something you said or did used for CiROCCO research purposes. There is a small risk in terms of entrusting your personal data to the research team. To mitigate any risk, we have outlined strict privacy and data management procedures, in line with the applicable National and EU regulations, including the requirements of the Regulation EU 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation)."

1. How important do you consider the problem of Desert Dust Storms (DDSs) in your area and why (frequency, severity etc.)?

2. Which stakeholder groups do you hold as key actors accountable for dealing with the problem of DDS events?

3. Can you identify any gaps in the current (local and/or National and/or EU) regulation for DDS, air pollution and the affected sectors (e.g. health)?

4. What is the capacity of your organization to tackle the problem of DDS events in your area? (Please reply only if you are representing a local or National Authority)

5. Which parameters are currently being measured in your area? Would additional in-situ data help tackle the problem of dust storms in your area?

6. Are you aware of any specific measures or practices that are in place to tackle the problem of DDS in your area? Are you aware of any relevant activities planned for the near future?

7. What do you think is missing from local population in order to be better prepared against upcoming DDS events? (awareness raising, training, situational awareness, personalised technological solutions / ICT tools, targeted policies etc.)

8. How does decision-making process of your Organisation to deal with DDS currently works? (Please reply only if you are representing a local or National authority)

Annex 3: Online survey results from the 2nd Stakeholders' Workshop

The graphical visualisation of the replies to the exploitation workshop (in English) and the online survey (in Serbian) is presented in this Annex.

If yes, could you tell us more about the service of the provider?

Video surveillance of Vojvodina	Real-time mapa koja prikazuje aktivne požare na teritoriji RS	Within Landsense project. Developed by GeoVila	It's a prevention system which warns of high fire risk (based on temperature, wind intensity etc)
Senzori za dim	Private market companies	Fire risk warning	

How may you benefit from a service that notifies you of a wildfire occurrence probability?

Avoid high risk areas	Brza reakcija	Avoiding high risk areas	Avoiding personal and material damage
Preventivno delovanje	avoid high risk activities	Prevent some activities	

How important for sustainable ecosystem management are these processes?

1st	Land use planning at decentralised and local levels
2nd	Financing mechanisms
3rd	High-level policies
4th	Realistic budget allocation

How may you benefit from sustainable ecosystem management?

1st	Access to clean air and water
2nd	Biodiversity preservation
3rd	Better nutrition and health
4th	Continuous provision of ecosystem goods

Are there any large forest ecosystems in your area?

no	Yes	Yes	Yes
Da	Yes	Yes	Yes

Would you like to participate in more sustainable land management of your area?

Yes	No	Not sure
12	0	0

Assume there is a citizen platform to choose an area, select a sustainable practice and vote for implementation

How much would you donate to see the selected practices implemented?

EUR 50 annually	EUR 200 or more annually	I would not pay for such an action
5	0	7

How would you describe the replicability/upscaling of the Land Use and Ecosystems Management service in the five years post-project?

High - CIRCO system can go global with this business service	Moderate - CIRCO system would need additional effort and funds to respond to other markets	Low - CIRCO system is a tailored solution, we should go for fee, but large contracts.
4	3	0

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

RHMZ	Ministarstvo životne sredine	SEPA	Agencija za životnu sredinu
Ministarstvo poljoprivrede	(National or regional) Operational centers for disaster management	Dvooper	

Can you suggest a Consultancy partner for this business service?

Zelena Stolica na republičkom nivou, ali i pokrajnska	Scientific Institute and Faculties	national forestry agency	ECMWF / COPERNICUS
Private institutes	Institut za biološka ispitivanja- Beograd	Biosence	

Can you suggest a Global partner for this business service?

EEA	WHO	NASA / ESA	Eco
WMO	Ecomanagement		

If you had an app on your computer called Land Use and Ecosystem Management Decision support system, how would you call it?

No	Ecomanagement	Land	LUEMDSS
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Vaš nivo obrazovanja:

Organizacija iz koje dolazite:

Kako biste okarakterisali problem zagađenja vazduha na Vašem području?

Kako biste okarakterisali problem opasnosti od požara u Vašem području?

Koliko smatrate da su usvojene mere i prakse dovoljno efikasne u cilju smanjenja uticaja zagađenja vazduha u Vašem području?

Koliko smatrate da su usvojene mere i prakse dovoljno efikasne u cilju smanjenja uticaja od opasnosti od požara u Vašem području?

Ocenite sledeće parametre po važnosti za praćenje kvaliteta vazduha, počevši od najvažnijih:

Koji od ovih parametara i uređaja su pogodni za monitoring kvaliteta vazduha i/ili otkrivanje požara i kreiranje preventivnih mera?

U kojim područjima Vojvodine bi CiROCCO sistem bio od najveće koristi?

Kakve prognoze CiROCCO sistema (u smislu vremenske rezolucije) biste voleli da vidite i koje bi Vam bile od pomoći?

Prema Vašem mišljenju, kome bi CIROCCO system bio od koristi?

Mentimeter

U poređenju sa postojećim meteorološkim stanicama, koje karakteristike CIROCCO senzorskog čvora Vam se čine jedinstvenim i privlačnim za upotrebu?

Mentimeter

Koje modele aktivnosti obuke/treninja smatrate prikladnim, kako biste na kraju efikasno usvojili rešenja predložena kroz pilot CIROCCO?

Mentimeter

Koje modele dokumentacije smatrate poželjnijim, kako bi se omogućilo kontinuirano učenje i efikasno usvajanje CIROCCO rešenja?

Mentimeter

Koje druge karakteristike/informacije, koje bi mogao da sadrži CIROCCO sistem, smatrate važnim za Vaš primer problema?

Use in urban environments

Izvor klimatskih podataka

Proširena lista parametara

Time history data

Mentimeter

Mentimeter

Annex 4: 2nd Stakeholders' Workshop – Questionnaire for written feedback

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts – CiROCCO

2nd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop 5th of December 2023

Grant Agreement Number: 101086497

Name³:

Organisation*:

Email*:

Age*: <20 / 21-30 / 31-40 / 41-50 / 51-60 / 61-70 / 71-80

Gender*: male / female / other

Location* (Country/City):

Education Level*: School / Bachelor / Masters / PhD / Other (please specify)

³ I consent to my contact details (First and Last Name, Organisation, etc.) being included in the list of participants.

- I understand that any personal data collected by CiROCCO will be kept strictly confidential, to the minimum necessary for the purpose.
- I understand my data subjects rights*
- I understand that my participation raises some small risks** in terms of entrusting my data to the research team.
- I consent to being filmed, audio recorded, and having notes taken of my activities and experiences during the workshop/webinar and consent to CiROCCO using this for its promotion.
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**"There is a small risk that you may share some confidential information by chance or that you may feel uncomfortable talking about some issues. You can inform us at any time, if you decide you do not want to have something you said or did used for CiROCCO research purposes. There is a small risk in terms of entrusting your personal data to the research team. To mitigate any risk, we have outlined strict privacy and data management procedures, in line with the applicable National and EU regulations, including the requirements of the Regulation EU 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation)."

Occupation*: Student (e.g. High-School or University) / Researcher / Employee / Not working (e.g. retired or unemployed)

1. How important is the management of natural resources in the Deliblato Sands and its surroundings, and why?

2. Which stakeholders do you consider important for issues of supporting habitat restoration in the field of environmental protection in Deliblato Sands and its surroundings?

3. Can you identify any gaps in the current (local and/or National and/or EU) regulation in the field of natural resource management and the affected sectors (e.g., environment, health)?

4. What is the capacity of your organization to tackle the problem of natural resource management in Deliblato Sands area? (Please reply only if you are representing a local or National authority)

5. Which parameters are currently being measured in Deliblato Sands area? Would additional in-situ data help tackle the problem of natural resource management in Deliblato Sands area?

6. Are you aware of any specific measures or practices that are in place to tackle the problem of natural resource management in Deliblato Sands area? Are you aware of any relevant activities planned for the near future?

7. What information do you think the citizens of Serbia, that is, the local population in the vicinity of Deliblato Sands, lack, regarding the prevention of degradation of the quality of the environment? (awareness raising, training, situational awareness, personalised technological solutions / ICT tools, targeted policies etc.)

8. Do you think that the results of CiROCCO would contribute to the improvement of natural resource management in the Deliblato Sands?

9. Do you think that the results of the CiROCCO project (low-cost sensors) could be applied in other sectors/areas of activity? If yes, please specify which one.

Annex 5: Online survey results from the 3rd Stakeholders' Workshop

The graphical visualisation of the replies to the integrated online survey is presented in this Annex.

Highest Education Level:

What is your organization type?

3. How would you characterize the impact of dust on solar radiation and energy production in your area?

4. How would you characterize the impact of dust on air quality in your area?

5. How sufficient do you consider the measures and practices adopted to minimize the impact of dust on solar radiation/energy production in your area?

6. How sufficient do you consider the measures and practices adopted to minimize the impact of dust on air quality in your area?

7. Please rate the following parameters in terms of importance for solar energy potential estimations, dust and air quality monitoring?

8. Which of these parameters promise to be useful to monitor dust, solar energy potential and air quality?

9. On average, how far from the measurement fields in areas of interest is the first available Wi-Fi access point or the nearest 4G/5G antenna?

10. What kind of forecasts from CiROCCO system (in terms of spatial resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

11. What kind of forecasts from CiROCCO system (in terms of temporal resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

12. Who do you think would need the CiROCCO system? (more than 1 replies possible)

13. Compared to existing environmental monitoring stations, which features of CiROCCO sensing node seem unique and attractive to you?

14. Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/ see fit, so that you efficiently uptake the solutions proposed through CiROCCO?

15. Which modalities of tool documentation you find preferable, so as to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CiROCCO solutions?

16. Which other features/information would you consider important for CiROCCO to provide to be more useful for your case?

16. Which other features/information would you consider important for CiROCCO to provide to be more useful for your case?

16. Which other features/information would you consider important for CiROCCO to provide to be more useful for your case?

How would you prioritize these sensor network qualities?

Are you aware of other tools that predict power generation based on solar radiation measurements?

If yes, can you tell us who the service provider is?

No	No one open access.	no	N/A
PVystPv casePsol Meteorologica website	N/A	Global solar atlas	

Can you name any early warning systems related to Desert Dust Storms?

No	NO	No	No
-	Not currently available. Only DDS forecasts are	No	Egyptian Meteorological Authority can help with this.

How do you suggest CIROCCO bridge between government & other Stakeholder more effectively?

More in person meetings.	Frequent workshops>User friendly platform	Frequent focus groups	National board with all stockholders
On site workshops will be effective	Webinars and personal meetings	Seminars at universities and research centers	Similar Workshops

How do you suggest CIROCCO bridge between government & other Stakeholder more effectively?

Stakeholder WorkshopsSite visitsMoUs	Consultation workshops or round tables or an online platform with access to all these stakeholders and communication tools such as newsletters and policy briefs etc.	Workshop,Seminar	Cooperation
Workshops	Web-based Platform	By quantifying the real deficiency in energy production and setting reports in losses in money due to dust effect abd illustrating some real case studies in another places	workshops, Seminars

How do you suggest CIROCCO bridge between government & other Stakeholder more effectively?

Key person from each entity	Spin off projects	Simple competitions	Institutional linkages with heading of multi involved ministers
--------------------------------	-------------------	---------------------	---

Can you name any meteorological sensors operating in harsh environments?

No	No	no	Geonica
I dont remember to be honest I worked with some sensors of ESA in Lapland, northern Finland which was a harsh environment in the boreal forest.	NA	Ammorit OR	Temperature

How would you describe the replicability/upscaling of the Renewable energy planning service in the five years post-project?

1

7

8

1 Low- CIROCCO system is a tailored solution, we should go far free; but large contracts.

7 Moderate- CIROCCO system would need additional effort and funds to expand to other markets

8 High- CIROCCO system can go global with this business service

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

Fernas Shuman Co.	Not at the moment	ORASCOMINFINITYACWA POWER MASDARSIEMENS	Solterm
no	GEF, UNDP.	No	Local investors

Annex 6: 3rd Stakeholders' Workshop - Questionnaire for written feedback

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts – CiROCCO

3rd CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop 22nd of January 2024

Grant Agreement Number: 101086497

Name⁴:

Organisation*:

Email*:

Age*: <20 / 21-30 / 31-40 / 41-50 / 51-60 / 61-70 / 71-80

Gender*: male / female / other

Location* (Country/City):

Education Level*: School / Bachelor / Masters / PhD / Other (please specify)

Occupation*: Student (e.g. High-School or University) / Researcher / Employee / Not working (e.g. retired or unemployed)

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1. How important do you consider the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy in your area (either in the pilot area (the Benban solar farm) or in another area of interest-please specify if so) and why (frequency, severity etc.)?

2. Which stakeholder groups do you hold as key actors accountable for dealing with the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy (e.g., Ministries, Research Institutes, SMEs, Government Agencies, NGOs, Regional/International Organisations, others)? (Please select one or more from the abovementioned entities or others not listed here and please be as specific as possible).

3. Can you identify any gaps in the current (local and/or National and/or EU) regulation in the field of (renewable) energy management, air pollution and the affected sectors (e.g. health, economy and the environment)?

4. What is the capacity of your organization to mitigate the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy in your area (either in the pilot area (the Benban solar farm) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? (Please reply only if you are representing a local, Regional or National authority)

5. Which parameters are currently being measured in your area (either in the pilot area (the Benban solar farm) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? Would additional in-situ data help mitigate the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy in your area?

6. Are you aware of any specific measures or practices that are in place to mitigate the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy in your area (either in the pilot area (the Benban solar farm) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? Are you aware of any relevant activities planned for the near future?

7. What information do you think local population in the vicinity of the Benban solar farm is missing, in order to be better aware of utilising renewable energy? (awareness raising, training, situational awareness, personalised technological solutions / ICT tools, targeted policies etc.)

8. How does decision-making process of your Organisation to deal with the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy currently works? (Please reply only if you are representing a local, Regional or National authority)

9. Do you think that the results of CiROCCO would contribute to the mitigation of the impact of dust on solar radiation and produced energy in the pilot area (the Benban solar farm)?

10. Do you think that the results of the CiROCCO project could be applied in other sectors/areas of activity? If yes, please specify which one.

Annex 7: Online survey results from the 4th Stakeholders' Workshop

The graphical visualisation of the replies to the online survey is presented in this Annex.

Education level?

Organisation?

How would you characterize the problem of air pollution in your area?

How would you characterize the problem of groundwater quality degradation in your area?

If you chose "Other", please indicate it

How sufficient do you consider the measures and practices adopted to mitigate air pollution in your area?

How sufficient do you consider the measures and practices adopted to mitigate groundwater quality degradation in your area?

Please rate the following parameters in terms of importance air quality monitoring starting from the most important:

Which of these parameters seem attractive to monitor air quality?

On average, how far from the measurement fields in areas of interest (either in the pilot area or in another area of interest) is the first available?

What kind of forecasts from CiROCCO system (in terms of spatial resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

If you chose "Other", please indicate it

Mediterraneo

What kind of forecasts from CiROCCO system (in terms of temporal resolution) would you like to see that would be helpful?

Who do you think would need the CiROCCO system?

If you chose "Other", please indicate it. Responses: All of them

todos los anteriores

todos los anteriores

Compared to existing environmental monitoring stations, which features of CiROCCO sensing node seem unique and attractive to you?

Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/see fit, so that you ultimately efficiently uptake the solutions proposed through the pilots

Which modalities of tool documentation you find preferable, so as to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CiROCCO solutions?

Which other features would you consider important to be provided by the CiROCCO system?

La conexión entre sensores, modelos satelitales y diseño de redes de control

Acceso a la información generada via web en mapas

Which problems can Modeling of GHGs and Particle emissions solve, which needs are we addressing?

Pronósticos ambientales para la planificación del medio ambiente y el territorio

How would you prioritize these sensor network qualities?

Are you aware of any tools that predict contamination and assess the quality of air and groundwater?

Si ha contestado si, ¿puede indicar el proveedor del servicio o software?

CAMs	Software de Agencia Española de Meteorología para calidad del aire. No conozco equivalente para la calidad del agua subterránea	canales oficiales	No conozco
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How do you propose we reach our government customers most effectively?

A través de sus servicios centrales.	AEMET
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Can you name any meteorological sensors operating in harsh environments?

aerosol lidars, ceilometers, Sun-photometers, Doppler lidars, particle samplers

How important for Modelling of GHGs and Particles Emissions are these processes?

How would you describe the replicability / up Modelling of GHGs and Particles Emissions service in the five years post-project?

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

AEMET	Muy alta	AEMET	AEMET, ACTRIS
AEMET, ACTRIS	Empresas e inversores del sector solar	Agencias de planificación de recursos naturales	Abengoa

Can you suggest a strategic partner for this business service?

Dust Alert

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Consultancy partner for this business service?

mpic

mpic

Mentimeter

Can you suggest a Global partner for this business service?

mpic

Mentimeter

If you had an app called Modelling GHG and Particles Emissions, how would you call it?

GHGparticles

Mentimeter

Mentimeter

Mentimeter

Annex 8: 4th Stakeholders' Workshop - Questionnaire for written feedback

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts –
CiROCCO

4th CiROCCO Stakeholders' Workshop 8th of March 2024

Grant Agreement Number: 101086497

Name *Nombre*⁵:

Organisation *Organización**:

Email *Correo electrónico**:

Age *Edad**: <20 / 21-30 / 31-40 / 41-50 / 51-60 / 61-70 / 71-80

Gender *Género**:

Male *Hombre*

Female *Mujer*

Other *Otro*

-
- ⁵ I consent to my contact details (First and Last Name, Organisation, etc.) being included in the list of participants.
- I understand that any personal data collected by CiROCCO will be kept strictly confidential, to the minimum necessary for the purpose.
 - I understand my data subjects rights*
 - I understand that my participation raises some small risks** in terms of entrusting my data to the research team.
 - I consent to being filmed, audio recorded, and having notes taken of my activities and experiences during the workshop/webinar and consent to CiROCCO using this for its promotion.
 - I understand that if I have any questions seeking further clarification or assurances about the ethical issues relating to the project, I am free to contact the Project Coordinator, Dr. Angelos Amditis.

*"You have the right to information regarding what is collected and processed, to access to your data being processed, to delete or make any changes to this information, and to restrict processing. You have the right to receive requested information in a time-limited fashion. If you are concerned or have questions about how your personal data is being processed, you have the right to contact both the Project Coordinator, Dr Angelos Amditis, and the communication Project manager, Ms. Kate Zouroufidou."

**"There is a small risk that you may share some confidential information by chance or that you may feel uncomfortable talking about some issues. You can inform us at any time, if you decide you do not want to have something you said or did used for CiROCCO research purposes. There is a small risk in terms of entrusting your personal data to the research team. To mitigate any risk, we have outlined strict privacy and data management procedures, in line with the applicable National and EU regulations, including the requirements of the Regulation EU 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation)."

Location (Country/City) Localización (País/Ciudad)*:

Education Level Nivel educativo*:

- School *Educación Primaria*
- Bachelor *Grado o licenciatura*
- Masters *Máster*
- PhD *Doctorado*
- Other (please specify) *Otros (por favor, especifique)*

Occupation Ocupación*:

- Student (e.g. High-School or University) *Estudiante (p.ej. bachillerato o Universidad)*
- Researcher *Investigador*
- Employee *Empleado*
- Not working (e.g. retired or unemployed) *Sin trabajo (desempleado o jubilado)*

1. How important do you consider the problem of air pollution in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so) and why? *¿Cómo de importante considera el problema de la contaminación del aire en su zona (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna) y por qué?*

2. How important do you consider the problem of groundwater quality degradation in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so) and why? *¿Cómo de importante considera el problema de la degradación de la calidad química del agua subterránea en su zona (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna) y por qué? y por qué?*

3. Which stakeholder groups do you hold as key actors accountable for dealing with the problem of GHGs and Particles Emissions (e.g., Ministries, Research Institutes, SMEs, Government Agencies, NGOs, Regional/International Organisations, others)? (Please select one or more from the abovementioned entities or others not listed here and please be as specific as possible)? *¿Qué grupos de interés considera como actores clave para hacer frente al problema gases de efecto invernadero y emisión de partículas (ej. ministerios, institutos de investigación, PIMEs, agencias de gobierno, ONGs, organizaciones regionales o internacionales, otros)? (Por favor, seleccione una o más de las opciones y sea tan específico como pueda)*

4. Can you identify any gaps in the current (local and/or National and/or EU) regulation in the field of air pollution management and the affected sectors (e.g., health, economy, the environment, etc.)? ¿Puede identificar algún vacío en la actual normativa (local y/o nacional y/o de la UE) en el ámbito de la contaminación atmosférica y los sectores afectados (p.ej., salud, medio ambiente, economía, etc.)?

5. What is the capacity of your organization to mitigate the air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? (Please reply only if you are representing a Local / Regional / National authority) *¿Cuál es la capacidad de su organización para mitigar el problema de la contaminación atmosférica (y/o en la degradación de las aguas subterráneas) en su zona (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna)? (Por favor, responda solo si representa a una autoridad local / regional / nacional)*

6. Which parameters are currently being measured in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? Would additional in-situ data help mitigate the impact of air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) in the region? *¿Qué parámetros qué se están midiendo actualmente en su región (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna) relacionados con estos problemas? ¿Ayudarían los datos adicionales sobre el terreno a abordar el problema de la contaminación atmosférica y la contaminación del agua en la región?*

1. Are you aware of any specific measures or practices that are in place to mitigate the impact of air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) on health, economy and the environment in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? Are you aware of any relevant activities planned for the near future? *¿Conoce alguna medida o práctica específica que se haya implementado para mitigar el impacto de la contaminación atmosférica en el medio ambiente, la salud y la economía en su zona (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna)? ¿Conoce alguna actividad planeada relevante en el futuro cercano?*

2. What information do you think is missing from the local population to be better aware of the impact of air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) on health, economy and the environment? (awareness raising, training, situational awareness, personalized technological solutions / information and communication tools (ICT), targeted policies etc.) *¿Qué información cree que le falta a la población local para estar mejor concienciada sobre el impacto de la contaminación atmosférica (y/o la degradación del agua subterránea) en la salud, la economía y el medio ambiente? (sensibilización, formación, conocimiento de la situación, soluciones tecnológicas personalizadas / herramientas de información y comunicación (ICT), políticas específicas, etc.)*

3. How does decision-making process of your Organization to deal with the impact of air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) on health, economy and the environment currently works? (Please reply only if you are representing a Local / Regional / National authority) *¿Cómo funciona actualmente el proceso de toma de decisiones de su organización para hacer frente al impacto de la contaminación atmosférica (y/o la degradación de la calidad del agua subterránea) en el medio ambiente, salud y economía? (Por favor, responda solo si representa a una autoridad local / regional / nacional)*

4. Do you think that the results of CiROCCO would contribute to the mitigation of the impact of air pollution (and/or groundwater quality degradation) on health, economy and the environment in your area (either in the pilot area (south-eastern Spain) or in another area of interest-please specify if so)? Why? *¿Cree que los resultados de CiROCCO contribuirían mitigar el impacto de la contaminación atmosférica (y/o la degradación de las aguas subterráneas) sobre la salud, la economía, y el medio ambiente en su área (tanto en el área piloto del sureste de España como en otra área de interés – por favor, especifique si se le ocurre alguna)? ¿Por qué?*

5. Do you think that the results of the CiROCCO project could be applied in other sectors / areas of activity? If yes, please specify which one. *¿Cree que los resultados del proyecto CiROCCO (sensores de bajo coste) podrían aplicarse en otros sectores / áreas de actividad? En caso afirmativo, sírvase indicar cuál.*